

Sectoral Patterns of Diffusion of Innovation Management Practices in Brazilian Manufacturing Firms

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The paper addresses the diffusion of innovation management practices (IMP) in Brazilian innovating firms in the manufacturing industry. The research on which it is based aimed at mapping out diffusion of IMP in a robust sample of Brazilian manufacturing firms and with a wide scope of IMP dimensions. The paper premise is the critique of innovation management literature which pursue universal ‘best practices’, meaning the adoption of the same tools and recipes in any firm, irrespective of sector or context. Thus, the paper investigates whether there are sectoral patterns in the diffusion of IMP in Brazilian manufacturing firms, according to Pavitt’s sectoral taxonomy of distinctive technological trajectories and related innovation management challenges and tasks. In order to investigate empirically these issues, a survey of an intentional sample of 65 innovative Brazilian firms was carried out in 2015/16. The survey comprised the application of an electronic structured questionnaire supported by visits and extensive interviews aimed at collecting evidence. Some findings support Pavitt’s understanding. As regards networking for R&D cooperation and technology transfer, while Science-based firms primarily source from universities, Scale-intensive firms primarily rely on suppliers and Specialized Suppliers present strong ties with customers. Yet, other findings are in contrast to Pavitt’s view and highlight the specific context of an emerging economy. Science based firms in Brazil present the lowest rate of adoption of IMP as compared to firms belonging to other technological trajectories. Public universities are the preferable partner for R&D cooperation for other trajectory groups and rank first in the aggregate sample.

1. Introduction

The aim of this paper is to contribute to the understanding of the main features in the diffusion of innovation management practices (IMP) in Brazil by exploring the possible constitution of sectorial patterns of diffusion of IMP in Brazilian innovating firms in the manufacturing industry.

Emerging country firms have considerably heightened their profile in the global innovation landscape in the past two decades and there is now a considerable literature dealing with this phenomenon. Yet, concern with challenges in the diffusion of innovation management and organizational practices in such firms has received much less attention. Recent research on the topic has been based on cases studies or has focused on specific management practices. This research aimed at mapping out diffusion of IMP in a more robust sample of Brazilian manufacturing firms and with a wide scope of IMP dimensions. We did not expect to find a homogeneous pattern of IMP. We departed from a critique of the innovation management literature which pursue universal ‘best practices’, meaning the adoption of the same tools and recipes in any firm, irrespective of sector or context.). Thus, the paper explores sectoral patterns of diffusion of IMP in Brazilian manufacturing firms in connection with Pavitt’s taxonomy of distinctive technological trajectories and related innovation management needs (Pavitt 1984; Tidd, Bessant and Pavitt 2005).

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The empirical investigation was based on the survey of an intentional sample of 65 Brazilian innovative, manufacturing firms which was carried out in 2015/16. Operational variables were defined in order to express IMP diffusion dimensions in the survey questionnaire: innovation management processes and tools, innovation networking practices and new organizational forms aimed at enhancing innovation capabilities. Survey comprised an electronic structured questionnaire supported by visits and extensive interviews.

Some findings support Pavitt’s understanding of how technology trajectories, comprising the nature of innovation activities, sources of knowledge and forms of appropriation forge management’s challenges in conducting the innovation project. However, structural limitations of innovation features and activities in the country account for findings pointing that there are relevant particularities in the diffusion of IMP in Brazilian manufacturing industry which are in contrast with Pavitt’s view. The paper is organized in six sections, including this introduction. Next section (Section II) discusses literature gaps concerning research on diffusion of IMP in emerging economies and sets the ground for delimitation of research issues, whereas Section III presents and justifies the conceptual framework for the investigation of sectoral patterns of diffusion of IMP. Section IV exposes research strategy and methods which were utilized in the Brazilian IMP survey. Findings of research are brought about and discussed in Section V, in the light of the framework designed in Section III. The concluding section discusses implications for further research and for policy.

2. Literature gaps addressed: the need for understanding innovation management capabilities in emerging countries

Emerging economies like Brazil, China and India have increased their participation in global innovation in the past two decades (Altenburg et al. 2008, Ernst 2008, Li and Kozhikode 2009). On the one hand, this is produce of the growth and globalization of firms originated in such counties, which in turn has been result of a long process of learning and accumulation of innovation capabilities (Ariffin and Figueiredo 2006, Bell and Figueiredo 2012, Williamson et al. 2013, Lema et al. 2015). On the other hand, foreign multinational corporations (MNC) have also contributed to this process, by enlarging innovation mandates and increasing R&D and innovation activities in subsidiaries located in such countries (Reddy 1997, 2102; Wang et al. 2012; Govindarajan and Trimble 2012). Such changes required the building of substantial technological capabilities, but this is not the entire picture.

In order to move up from production capabilities to advanced innovation capabilities (Bell 2009) as basis for competitive strategy and growth, firms in emerging economies need to undergo a process of organizational transformation which is an enabling factor for dealing with systemic innovation processes. Inspired by Bloom and Van Reenen (2007), substantial progress in the measurement of management capabilities at firm level and across sectors and countries¹ has allowed quantitative investigation of the correlation between managerial and organizational capabilities, innovation performance and the impact of R&D on innovation (Cirera and Maloney 2017). The World Bank study on the “Innovation Paradox” argues that an important obstacle to developing countries’ innovation and technological catching up lies on their lack of managerial capabilities, which are an essential complement to investment on R&D and innovation activities. They have stressed the importance of firm capabilities to identify market and technological opportunities, to select and develop plans and projects to exploit them and to cultivate the necessary human resources to successfully carry out innovation projects. In emerging countries, the change of business firms’ strategic focus from the sole operational excellence required from imitators to the cross-functional learning and creativity required from innovators is a process of transformation of their own organizational architecture: strategies, structures, governance of technology and innovation, decision-making processes and management routines (Quadros et al. 2017).

Yet, while there has been substantial research on innovation capabilities and technological catching up in emerging country firms, concern with the challenges they face in developing innovation management and related organizational skills have received little attention. The few exceptions (Quadros et al. 2013, Nagano et al. 2014, Zhang 2014, Bagno et al. 2015) are based on cases studies and/or focused on specific management practices, such as innovation project management. Chaterjee and Sahasranamam (2014) suggest that research on innovation management in India is limited and incipient.

¹ See World Management Survey (<http://worldmanagementsurvey.org/>), for cross country experience, Management and Organizational Practices Survey (MOPS) (<https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/mops.html>), for the United States Census Bureau’s initiative and Encuesta Nacional sobre Productividad y Competitividad de las Micro, Pequeñas y Medianas Empresas (ENAPROCE) (http://www.inegi.org.mx/est/contenidos/proyectos/encuestas/establecimientos/otras/enaproce/default_t.aspx), for the Mexican Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía’s survey focused on SME managerial capabilities.

The survey at firm level on which this paper is based² has set out to map the diffusion of IMP in a robust sample of Brazilian innovating manufacturing firms, across a large number of sectors and a wide a wide range of management practices. The survey initiative was motivated by objectives which were similar to those of the WB study as presented above. Departing from the premise that the quality of management influences the effectiveness of investment on R&D and other innovation activities, in terms of innovation performance and its economic impacts, the survey intended to measure firms’ innovation-related managerial and organizational capabilities. Thus, instead of focusing on inputs for and output of innovation, as is in innovation surveys following the OECD guidelines, the mentioned survey has targeted the process of innovation and the managerial capabilities it requires. Indicators of diffusion of IMP have been developed as measure of such capabilities.

As regards defining the specific managerial and organizational practices which are comprised within the category of IMP in this research, we have drawn on Adams et al. (2006) who proposed a set of dimensions to measure innovation management adoption. Moreover, we have also drawn on the most disseminated and comprehensive approaches to innovation management (Tidd et al. 2005, Hansen and Birkinshaw 2007, Burgelman et al. 2008, Schilling 2017). In line with those approaches, a reference model for the strategic management of technological innovation has been designed in order to set the scope of IMP in this research, including the following dimensions (Figure 1): 1. Organization and Governance of Innovation and R&D (high level leadership involvement; structure and organizational forms for innovation activities and decision-making; and human resources management practices aimed at innovation); 2. Innovation and Technology Strategy (strategy design and formalization); 3. Innovation management processes and tools (comprising: ideation; innovation project assessment, selection and monitoring; portfolio management; technology intelligence and foresight and competitive and marketing intelligence); and 4. Innovation networking (management of networks for technology transfer, R&D cooperation, technology services and management of intellectual property).

Figure 1 – Reference Model of Strategic Management of Technological Innovation

As a first attempt to measuring IMP diffusion in Brazil, the survey was meant as part of an exploratory research intended to allow for designing and testing categories, variables and indicators in an area plenty of polysemic terms. Thus, in addition to producing data, the survey was also planned as a learning process conducting to simpler and more precise categories and indicators, which could in a subsequent phase be applied to measure innovation management capabilities in the population of firms. From the beginning, the research team intended to grasp the broad picture of what Brazilian managers do when they organize for and manage innovation in manufacturing firms, which required that the inquiry addressed a sample of experienced innovating firms, as explained in section 4. Departing from a comprehensive reference model (Figure 1), the survey intended to identify and measure the level of intensity of diffusion of a diversified set of IMP in Brazilian firms: what were the most and the less disseminated processes and tools related to innovation management? What was the intensity and diversity of technological cooperation ties of the surveyed firms with suppliers, customers and research institutions? Were they less pronounced than developed country firms’ ties? What was the time

² See section 4 for an account of empirical research methodology.

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horizon and level of formalization (target setting) of the innovation strategy planning in Brazilian innovative firms? What was the nature and hierarchical level of R&D and innovation units within firms and how committed were firms’ high leadership with innovation?

3. Research issues: are there sectoral patterns of diffusion of IMP in Brazilian manufacturing? An analytical framework using Pavitt’s taxonomy

Two firm attributes have been taken into account in the stratification of the IMP survey of Brazilian innovative firms. On the one hand, sample segmentation according to the nationality of firm equity control (foreign x Brazilian) was recommendable, as it would allow further research on the contribution and limitations of MNC subsidiaries in Brazil to the building of innovation capabilities in the country, therefore adding to a long-standing debate (Quadros et al. 2001, Franco and Quadros 2003, Zanata and Queiroz 2007, Rocha and Ruiz 2010, Wellhausen 2013). Given the market leadership and pronounced profile in innovation performance of foreign MNC in most high and medium technology intensive sectors of Brazilian manufacturing, we have explored elsewhere their role in the diffusion of IMP and in the building of innovation-related managerial and organizational capabilities in Brazil (Quadros et al. 2017).

On the other hand, the size of the sample of the Brazilian IMP survey allowed for substantial sectoral diversification, which has created the opportunity to investigate sectoral patterns of IMP diffusion. Why is this relevant for research? Broad and comprehensive reference models for innovation management and organization, as the one presented in Figure 1 above, are useful tools for practitioners and researchers for delineating the boundaries of innovation management and establishing the major groups of practices and the interactions between them. However, they lack the analytical sharpness to contribute to the understanding of the relations between the adoption of particular managerial and organizational practices and the pattern of innovation-based competition at sector level. Tidd and Thuriaux-Aleman (2016) criticize the innovation management literature which pursue universal ‘best practices’, meaning the adoption of the same tools and recipes in any firm, irrespective of sector or context. Based on a pioneering survey of IMP adoption in a sample of 292 firms across 10 groups of industrial sectors in more than 16 countries, they have found significant differences in the adoption of different IMP practices across industry groups.

In this research, we set out to verify whether there is distinctiveness in the intensity and diversity of adoption of IMP between different manufacturing sectors, but we also intended to understand whether patterns of IMP adoption would be related with sectorial innovation dynamics and trajectories. This has led us to adopt Pavitt’s taxonomy of innovation trajectories (Pavitt 1984, 1992, Pavitt et al. 1989). The Pavitt taxonomy distinguishes innovative firms according to their technological trajectories, which comprises the nature of innovation activities, predominant type of innovation (cumulative or disruptive), their major internal and external sources for innovation and forms of appropriation. In the 1992 article, Pavitt also stressed the distinctive challenges faced by management in firms belonging to different trajectories. In its first proposition, focusing on manufacturing (Pavitt 1984), Pavitt taxonomy comprised 4 innovative firm trajectories³:

Science-based firms: their main source of technology is the internal R&D department, but nature and type of innovation also favors their links with research institutions; they seek opportunities horizontally, in related markets, or downstream in user sectors; thus major challenge for managers is developing complementary skills and resources required to extend their technologies to new markets; typical firms are in sectors such as pharmaceuticals, aircraft, microelectronics and advanced materials;

Scale-intensive firms: main source of technological knowledge are the design and engineering departments, even though specialized suppliers are also important source; major opportunities are related to production technologies involving complex and largescale manufacturing systems, but product innovation may also be an important source of competitive advantage; thus, major challenge for management is keeping leadership in productivity gains associated with product differentiation; typical firms are in sectors related to large scale process industries exploring natural resources (mining, oil & gas, pulp and paper), bulk intermediate material (petrochemicals and steel) and mass assembly industries (automotive, consumer electronics);

Specialized suppliers: main sources of technology are internal engineering and product design departments in association with customers/users, which are their primary source of opportunities; therefore, management’s priority agenda is to do

³ Following his first article, Pavitt has further elaborated this taxonomy by creating a fifth trajectory, namely information-intensive firms, which allowed for the inclusion of many types of service firms which could not be properly classified in his original contribution (Pavitt et al. 1989, Pavitt 1992). We do not deal with such category in this research, as there is no information-intensive firm in the validated sample.

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with establishing effective ties with clients; specialized suppliers are typically providers of mechatronic machinery and instruments, chemical and biological specialties, customized software and integrated, multi-technology solutions;

Supplier-dominated firms: main sources of technology are specialized suppliers (machinery and materials), even though design departments are the critical source for product innovation; major opportunities are horizontal, as regards product innovation and upstream, as to process innovation; therefore, a crucial management challenge is the integration of internal, multi-functional skills (marketing, product design, manufacturing) and suppliers’ skills; supplier-dominated firms are found in traditional consumer sectors such as textiles and apparel, footwear and housing construction.

The Pavitt taxonomy seems to have held its analytical power and influenced current research on innovation. Archibugi’s essay on the strength of the taxonomy sixteen years after formulation points out some of the stakes of its substantial dissemination. First, its high level of aggregation allows for relative simplicity as it maximizes differences between groups of firms, as opposed to very disaggregated classifications. Second, it is a taxonomy which has been elaborated to classify innovating firms, as opposed to other economic classifications meant to cover the entire population (innovating and non-innovating firms) (Archibugi 2001). The latter point suggests a strong adequacy of the Pavitt taxonomy to this research, as its methodological design has focused only innovating firms. Castellacci (2008) stressed a crucial point in Pavitt’s taxonomy which is possibly more important today, in the context of the increasing importance of external linkages between firms and institutions for innovation. This is its strong emphasis on the vertical links between suppliers, producers and users and the horizontal ties between firms and public research, particularly for Science-based firms.

4. Research Design and Methodology

The empirical investigation of the issues discussed in this paper is based on data provided by the Primar-2015 survey (CGEE 2016), which focused on producing indicators of IMP diffusion and capabilities in Brazil. Primar was a survey of an intentional sample of 65 Brazilian firms, mostly in manufacturing, which was carried out between August 2015 and December 2015 and April 2016. The survey was based on a structured questionnaire comprising the 4 dimensions of IMP presented in section II and the addition of a few questions on R&D expenditure, innovation performance and innovation impacts. Even though the questionnaire was electronically available to interviewees in advance, the finalization of it was based on visits and live interviews carried out by a couple of interviewers. Interviews were meant to discuss and explain doubts concerning the categories and definitions of IMP and to gather empirical evidence of adopted IMP in order to support responses. Thus visits and interviews actually led to significant changes in the first round of responses provided by firms before interviews. Senior managers in R&D and innovation areas of firms were in charge of filling in questionnaire and participating in interviews and revision of filled questionnaire.

Sample design was based on the inclusion criterion that firm was substantially experienced in innovation issues and had a record of adoption of IMP. In this respect, the intent was not to design a sample which were representative of Brazilian manufacturing firms in general, and not even of Brazilian innovating firms. The objective was to produce a sample of firms experienced in performing IMP. As most firms with such profile are also amongst the top R&D and innovation activity performers, it would be correct to conclude that the sample comprises a robust parcel of top Brazilian manufacturing firms. The sample was segmented in order to include the distinctive technological trajectories, according to Pavitt’s taxonomy, as well as different capital ownership nationality (national x foreign). Most firms are in the manufacturing industry, but a few local suppliers of customized software have been included as part of the specialized suppliers sub-sample (Table 1).

An important contribution of the Primar survey has been the design of a system of simple and composite indicators as means to quantify and normalize to a common scoring scale from 1 to 10 all questionnaire variables, including categorical ones. Indicators have been calculated considering simple and weighted arithmetic averages for both sets of 1 attributes: technological trajectories and nationality of capital ownership (foreign x national). Averages have been submitted to nonparametric variance tests.

Table 1 - Sample composition

Technological Trajectory	National Firms	Multinational Subsidiaries	Total
Science-based firms	10	5	15
Scale-intensive firms	12	13	25
Specialised Suppliers	10	3	13
Supplier-dominated firms	7	5	12
Total	39	26	65

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

5. Research findings and discussion

5.1 Diffusion of Innovation Management Processes and Tools

As regards the composite (aggregate) indicator of intensity and diversity in the diffusion of tools for innovation processes management (Pi-IntTool), data produced by the Brazilian IMP survey indicate that Specialised Suppliers present the highest rate of adoption, whereas Science-based firms are in the bottom of all groups of firms per trajectory (Table 2). Considering the main features of technological trajectories and related management challenges, as presented in section 3, it is not surprising that Specialized Suppliers lead in the rate of diffusion of process tools, but it was expected that Science-based firms were at the same level or above. These are the two groups of firms which present the highest technological intensity (as measured by the ratio R&D/sales) and are closer to the scientific frontier. It has been supposed that greater complexity in technology and in R&D and engineering activities would require greater intensity and diversity in the adoption of innovation management tools.

Table 2 Composite Indicator of Intensity and Diversity in the Use of Tools in Innovation Management Processes (Pi-IntTool) - Arithmetic mean score of sample firms by technological trajectory

Technological Trajectory	Mean score*	s
Science-based firms	3,3	1,7
Scale-intensive firms	4,4	2,0
Specialised Suppliers	4,7	1,7
Supplier-dominated firms	4,1	2,0
Sample	4,1	1,9

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

* Shaded cells indicate statistically significant mean score differences

The disaggregation of the composite indicator of intensity of tool adoption into its single indicator components reveals considerable dispersion in rates of adoption of tools per type of process, while it confirms the leadership of Specialised Suppliers and the bottom place of Science-based firms across most processes (Figure 2). Indeed, Specialised Suppliers lead in the intensity and diversity of adoption of tools in 3 out of 4 processes, which correspond to tools for ideation (Pi-Ideation Tool), for evaluation, monitoring and selection of single projects (Pi-Selection Tool) and for technology monitoring and foresight (Pi-TechIntelligence Tool), while Science-based firms are behind all other trajectory groups in

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adoption of tools across the entire range of processes (Figure 2). A possible explanation for Science-based firms’ lagging behind in (the use of processes and tools of) innovation management in Brazil is that until recently Brazilian firms (either local or MNC subsidiaries) in sectors such as electronics and pharmaceuticals have pursued a strategy of transfer of foreign technologies with incremental adaptation, which required only a fraction of R&D and innovation effort made by global product innovators in their markets⁴. Thus the complexity and diversity of innovation management requirements seem to lessen in line with lower levels of innovation capabilities, showing that the country context is an important aspect conditioning sectors and trajectories as far as the diffusion of IMP is concerned.

Figure 2 Component Indicators of the Composite Indicator of Intensity and Diversity in the Use of Tools in Innovation Management Processes (ip-IntTool) by Technological Trajectory

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

Another useful way to explore data of the Brazilian IMP survey in order to understand context particularities is by comparing rates of diffusion per processes and tools, in addition to diffusion per technological trajectory. Among the components of the indicator of intensity and diversity in the diffusion of tools for innovation processes management (Pi-IntTool), the indicator of intensity and use of evaluation and project selection tools (Pi-SelectionTool) and the indicator of intensity and diversity in the use competitive intelligence tools (Pi-CompetitionIntelligenceTool) presented the highest value on the survey scale for the aggregate sample (4.4), while the equivalent indicator for technological intelligence tools showed the lowest value (3.9). This is produced by the fact that major concern in innovation activities in Brazilian manufacturing lies on incremental, new product/process innovation, which favors the diffusion of tactic management practices rather than that of strategic management practices.

Disaggregation of data per diffusion of specific tools add evidence to this argument. Within the group of tools related to the process of innovation project evaluation, monitoring and selection, Stage-gate and Innovation Funnel techniques rank first in terms of number of users in the sample stratum for all trajectory strata, followed not far by PMI techniques (Figure

⁴ In the case of human and veterinary pharmaceuticals, this picture has slowly started to change from the adoption of government regulation for generic drugs in Brazil, which has opened a substantial market for local pharmaceutical groups which are required to perform at least the final steps of drug development (stage 2 and 3 clinical research). From producing generic drugs with minor adaptation, a few of the local groups moved towards developing new drugs based on proprietary technologies, mostly by combining active ingredients or exploring biological routes. However, this is a relatively recent move and the critical feature of firms operating in Brazil in electronics and pharma – which constitute the largest population amongst Science-based firms in the country - is the rather imitative nature of their innovations, mostly based on rolling out into Brazil products which have been developed elsewhere.

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3)5. To be sure, the diffusion of Stage-gate and Innovation Funnel techniques is the highest in the sample as a whole as compared to any other tool or technique related to any of the processes in the IMP survey. Such prominence of tools which are meant to the management of incremental product and process innovation suggests that market pulled, incremental innovation is the major focus of most Brazilian companies which are experienced in innovation and adopters of IMP. In contrast, techniques such as “spiral methods”, which are more oriented towards development of innovation projects with higher level of uncertainty and risk, as for instance development of new, proprietary technologies in technical areas which are new to the firm, present a very modest number of users (Figure 3), reinforcing the argument above. Among the groups of tools with lower levels of diffusion, is worth mentioning two cases of exception when trajectories are considered. The most evident case is ‘agile methods’, which present a high level of diffusion in the group of Specialised Suppliers, which is result of the fact that those methods have been strongly disseminated in Brazilian software firms, which represent a substantial share in this the group. It is also worth noticing that the level of diffusion of concurrent engineering practices is substantially high in the group of scale-intensive firms, which reveals the weight of consumer electronics and automotive manufacturing firms in this stratum and the fact that such firms are considerably updated in the adoption of methods to integrate product and process development.

Figure 3 - Relative frequency of users of tools and techniques for evaluation, selection and management of R & D and innovation projects by Technological Trajectory

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

⁵ Though not specific to the context of innovation projects, PMI/PMBOK are very disseminated in monitoring R7d and innovation projects in Brazil, at least in less detailed or orthodox versions.

Exploring disaggregation of diffusion of tools in the group which presents the lowest rate of diffusion, that is, tools related to technological intelligence and foresight (Pi-TechIntelligence Tool) also adds to the argument in this section. In a broad definition, the process of technology intelligence is to do with prospecting opportunities and threats in technology areas which are currently or potentially relevant to the business. It comprises practices which primarily aim at contributing to design of possible futures, although the horizon of such prospecting might vary in connection with nature and time span of product cycles and to the commitment of the firm with long term planning. Technology leaders and trend makers need to assume a long-term perspective, as much as followers focused on incremental innovation tend to be more focused on the short term. In the Brazilian IMP survey data, it should be noted first that the frequency of user of techniques and tools of technology intelligence in the whole sample is significantly lower than the frequency of users of tools related to the other processes, in line with the scores of diffusion as commented above in this section (Figure 4). Moreover, data suggest that more elaborated and/or long-term oriented practices, such as scenarios design and patent information trend analyses are considerably less diffused than simpler practices aiming at raising awareness and understanding of emerging issues, such as ad-hoc workshops and consultation involving technology experts. Again, this in line with and reinforces the character of innovation processes in most Brazilian innovating firms. Brazilian firms like Petrobras, Embraer, Weg and few others, which are committed to proprietary technological innovation and new market creation and therefore are concerned with prospecting technological opportunities are rare, in a population whose horizon is short to medium term and focus is solely in supply demand as is. Nevertheless, it is also noticeable that 2/3 of science -based and supplier-dominated firms have responded to be users of methods of patent-based technology trend analyses. In the case of Science-based firms, this would be expected and may be boosted by the fact that in pharma and veterinary firms consultation of patent data is mandatory at individual project level in order to avoid breaking of third parties’ IP rights.

Figure 4 - Relative frequency of users of tools and techniques of technology intelligence by Technological Trajectory

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

5.2 Networking Practices for Access to Technology and R&D Cooperation

Section 3 has delineated what would be the pattern which could be expected of each trajectory group in terms of types and relevance of innovating firms’ external links as sources of technology and insights for innovation. In this section, we draw on results of the Brazilian IMP survey to understand whether and to what extent such patterns are found in Brazilian innovating firms or are modified by the country context.

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In this regard, the most striking finding of the Brazilian IMP survey is the very high profile attributed to Brazilian public universities as partners for R&D cooperation by sample firms, as 41 out of 65 responding firms (63%) declared they have established R&D partnership agreements with such institutions, which has been important contribution to their innovation process. The magnitude of such finding in this special sample of experienced, innovating firms can be measured by comparing with data produced by the Brazilian innovation survey (PINTEC). According to the 2014 Brazilian innovation survey, only 3,3% of innovating manufacturing firms and 25% of manufacturing firms performing R&D had cooperation ties with universities for R&D and/or product testing trials in 2014 (IBGE 2016). Moreover, all groups of sample firms by technological trajectory have presented high profile of diffusion of R&D cooperation engagement with public universities as measured by the number of firms engaged in such cooperation per trajectory stratum. While in the group of Science-based firms, as expected, engagement with public universities ranks first in terms of frequency of engagement per type of institution for R&D cooperation, they are also the most frequent engagement in the group of Scale-intensive firms and third, in the other two groups (Figure 5).

The Brazilian innovation literature has pointed out the relevance of academic research in the context of business innovation in the country. There are a number of determinants contributing to this phenomenon. Overall, Brazilian innovating firms (either controlled by nationals or by foreign MNC) have accumulated neither culture, nor capabilities nor technological infra-structure for technological research. R&D and innovation activities comprise rather the use of available knowledge for product and process development than creation of knowledge or new combinations of knowledge. Therefore, in search for solutions of technological problems emerging in NPD projects it is not uncommon that firms turn to university labs and research groups as a second best for the missing applied research unit (Quadros et al. 2014, Suzigan and Vasconcellos ?). Some firms seek in universities access to knowledge related to technologies which are new to them, as in the case of second generation ethanol technologies (Bueno 2015). More recently, innovation policy programs to promote university-firm partnership have multiplied at both federal and state government levels, attracting more firms to partnering with universities. To firms interested in internally developing research capabilities, long-term ties with academic graduate and research programs can be an interesting and gradual way to internalize and socialize scientific while they are still in their formation phase.

In spite of the findings commented above which seems to be substantially conditioned by the country context, it is also interesting to notice that the sort and relevance of external sources per trajectory group, as measured by the relative frequency of partnership agreements is overall consistent with the vertical and horizontal ties typical of the Pavitt taxonomy, as discussed in section 3. Therefore, in the group of Science-based firms, public universities and public research labs are the preferable ties, whereas Scale-intensive firms, in addition to engaging horizontally with universities, are preferably engaged vertically with suppliers of machinery and materials, and components and Specialised Suppliers are preferably engaged with customers and suppliers of materials and components (Figure 5). The odd case here is the group of Supplier-dominated firms, which have not indicated suppliers as preferable engagement. Such finding could be possibly influenced by a large presence of firms operating in the electric energy sector in this group, with large presence of MNC subsidiaries and a legal obligation of engaging with Brazilian public research institutions.

Figure 5- Relative frequency of firms in R&D partnership agreements per partner category by technological trajectory

Source: Primar survey (CGEE 2016)

In regard to the engagement of survey firms in agreements for technology transfer from third parties, either by means of patent licensing, technology and know-how supply or technical assistance services, the picture is distinctive from the case of R&D partnership as discussed above. First, as preferable partner for technology sourcing, considering the frequency of engagement per partner in the aggregate sample, suppliers rank first, while public universities are second and very close to the third preference, which is headquarters. This suggests that firms value universities rather for their scientific knowledge and research skills than for their technological know-how and IP assets. As far as engagement patterns per technological trajectory is concerned, it appears that firms are closer to the behavior proposed in Pavitt’s taxonomy: suppliers of IP assets and universities rank first in the frequency of engagement for Science-based firms, suppliers, headquarters and universities abroad are first and second engagement preference for Scale-intensive firms and suppliers and customers are first and second for Specialised-suppliers. Brazilian public universities are not well ranked as partners for technology transfer for Scale-intensive firms and Specialised suppliers.

Figure 6- Relative frequency of firms engaged in technology transfer from 3rd parties per 3rd party category by technological trajectory

6. Conclusions

Research on innovation management capabilities and the diffusion of IMP in emerging countries is still in its early stages. However, the knowledge produced by the Brazilian IMP survey suggests that this is a promising way to deepen the understanding of limitations of emerging country firms catching up in innovation. We hope to have produced evidence enough to sustain the argument that sectoral patterns of diffusion of IMP in Brazilian innovating firms surely are influenced by firms’ technological trajectories, but in a manner, which is substantially influenced by the country context. In this connection, it seems that technological innovation capabilities, IMP diffusion and innovation management capabilities follow the same pace and interact. In order to understand the basic features of the diffusion of innovation management processes and tools, the particular limitations in the vision, targets and aims of Brazilian firms’ innovation processes need to be taken into account: overall, a short-term vision, geared to adapting and innovating to keep business as it is, prevails. Therefore, the diffusion of market oriented, tactical tools (such as stage-gate techniques, market research-based intelligence) is much more pronounced than the diffusion of technology creation oriented, strategic tools. And yet, this picture and related entrepreneurial vision is not a fatalistic or structural imposition, but the produce of a more or less aware choice of high leadership.

Two important leads are perceived for future research. On the one side, it is important to continue with the route of IMP surveys, but with simpler and sharper questions and indicators so that they could be applied to larger samples of firms. On the other side, a better understanding of the role of high leadership and of the governance of strategy and innovation could be an important subsidy for policy-makers and business leaders to promote the transformation in Brazilian business firms into more ambitious, effectively innovating corporations.

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